

Enhancing the Sustainability of Concrete: The Contribution of Recycled Steel Fibers to Mechanical Performance

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to investigate the effect of adding waste steel fibers on the mechanical properties of reinforced concrete. Reinforced concrete is a crucial construction material widely used in various projects; however, it is prone to cracking due to tensile stress, especially under harsh environmental conditions or dynamic loading. The utilization of steel fibers as an additive in reinforced concrete mixtures has gained attention as a method to improve crack resistance and mechanical performance. This research identifies several key issues, including optimizing the percentage of waste steel fibers, evaluating their effects on different concrete properties, and assessing their adaptability in large-scale construction practices. An experimental approach was employed to test various percentages of waste steel fibers relative to coarse aggregates in reinforced concrete mixtures. The research methodology includes material preparation, concrete mixing, testing of fresh and hardened concrete, data analysis, and result interpretation. Fresh concrete was tested for workability using the slump test, while hardened concrete samples were subjected to compressive and tensile strength tests after the designated curing period. The collected data were analyzed using a descriptive approach to evaluate the impact of waste steel fiber addition on the mechanical properties of reinforced concrete. The results indicate that adding 0.5% waste steel fiber is the optimal composition, increasing the tensile strength from 1.82 MPa to 2.13 MPa. Although the compressive strength decreased to 25.45 MPa, it still met the design requirement of 25 MPa. This study provides valuable insights into the application of steel fibers in reinforced concrete, contributing to the development of more efficient and sustainable construction practices.

Keywords: Crack Resistance, Mechanical Properties, Reinforced Concrete, Steel Fiber Waste, Sustainable Construction.

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INTRODUCTION

Steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) has garnered significant attention due to its enhanced mechanical properties, particularly in flexural strength, ductility, and impact resistance. The incorporation of steel fibers into concrete improves its post-cracking behavior and mitigates the brittle nature of conventional concrete [1-2]. Various studies have investigated the effects of different types

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of steel fibers, including those derived from industrial waste and recycled materials, on the performance of SFRC [3-7].

Recent research has highlighted the advantages of utilizing waste steel fibers, such as those obtained from lathe machine scraps, as a sustainable alternative to conventional reinforcement materials [8-9]. These fibers not only enhance the mechanical properties of concrete but also contribute to reducing environmental waste [10-12].

The ductility and flexural behavior of SFRC have been widely studied, with findings indicating that the fiber content, shape, and distribution significantly influence the overall structural performance [13-14]. Moreover, the hybridization of different fiber types has been explored to optimize mechanical performance, particularly in enhancing impact resistance and reducing crack propagation [15-16].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Research Methodology

This study employs an experimental approach to investigate the effect of incorporating steel fiber waste on the mechanical properties of reinforced concrete. The research methodology includes variable determination, material preparation, concrete mixing, mechanical testing, and data analysis.

2. Variables

- Independent Variables: Proportion of steel fiber waste in the concrete mix (0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%), type and size of steel fibers.
- Dependent Variables: Compressive strength, tensile strength, and testing time of the samples.

3. Equipment and Materials

3.1 Equipment

The equipment and functions used in this research are as follows:

Table 1. Equipment and Functions

No.	Equipment	Function
1	Stopwatch	Measures time during testing
2	Measuring tape	Measures slump collapse
3	Cement spoon	Transfers materials
4	Wheelbarrow	Transports materials and samples
5	Balance scale	Weighs materials
6	Digital scale	Ensures accurate weight measurement
7	Pycnometer	Tests specific gravity and water absorption of fine aggregates
8	Tray	Holds materials during testing
9	Graduated cylinder	Measures water volume
10	Sieve	Filters aggregates
11	Bucket	Holds water or aggregates
12	Truncated cone	Determines fine aggregate properties
13	Steel cylinder	Measures bulk density of aggregates
14	Abrams cone	Tests fresh concrete properties
15	Oven	Dries aggregates
16	Los Angeles machine	Tests aggregate abrasion resistance
17	Cylindrical mold	Forms concrete samples (15x30 cm)
18	Concrete mixer	Mixes concrete materials
19	Universal Testing Machine	Conducts compressive and tensile strength tests

3.2 Materials

The materials used in this study include:

- Cement

- Sand
- Gravel
- Water
- Steel fiber waste

Figure 1. Steel fiber

4. Experimental Procedure

4.1 Sample Preparation

- The steel fibers were prepared and uniformly distributed in the concrete mix.
- Concrete mixtures were prepared according to SNI or ACI standards.
- Three variations of steel fiber waste content were used: 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% of the coarse aggregate weight.
- A control sample without steel fiber waste was also prepared for comparison.

4.2 Testing Procedures

- Fresh Concrete Testing: The slump test was conducted to assess workability.
- Hardened Concrete Testing: Samples were cured for a designated period before testing compressive and tensile strength.
- Mechanical Testing: A Universal Testing Machine was used to determine compressive and splitting tensile strength.

RESULTS

The results obtained from testing the physical properties of sand and gravel materials, fresh concrete and cylindrical samples are as follows:

Table 2. Physical Properties of Sand and Gravel

Properties	Sand	Gravel
Water content	1.95%	0.40%
Bulk Specific Gravity	2.51	2.65

Apparent Specific Gravity	2.62	2.72
SSD Specific Gravity	2.55	2.67
Absorption	1.61%	0.96%
Volume weight	1.54 kg/dm ³	1.38 kg/dm ³
Volume weight fresh concrete	2.38 kg/dm ³	
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 0.5%	2.35 kg/dm ³	
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 1.0%	2.39 kg/dm ³	
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 1.5%	2.27 kg/dm ³	

Figure 2. Sieve Analysis of Sand

Figure 3. Sieve Analysis of Gravel

Table 2. Properties of Fresh Concrete

Volume weight fresh concrete	2.38 kg/dm ³
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 0.5%	2.35 kg/dm ³
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 1.0%	2.39 kg/dm ³
Volume weight fresh concrete + SF 1.5%	2.27 kg/dm ³
Slump fresh concrete	84.33 mm
Slump fresh concrete + SF 0.5%	76.67 mm

Slump fresh concrete + SF 1.0%	102.00 mm
Slump fresh concrete + SF 1.5%	100.00 mm
Water absorption of concrete cylinder	0.85%
Water absorption of concrete cylinder + SF 0.5%	0.69%
Water absorption of concrete cylinder + SF 1.0%	0.64%
Water absorption of concrete cylinder + SF 1.5%	0.61%

Table 3. Average Compressive and Split Tensile Strength of Concrete Cylinders

Compressive strength of concrete	27.16 MPa
Compressive strength of concrete + SF 0.5%	25.45 MPa
Compressive strength of concrete + SF 1.0%	24.89 MPa
Compressive strength of concrete + SF 1.5%	20.55 MPa
Split tensile strength of concrete	1.82 MPa
Split tensile strength of concrete + SF 0.5%	2.13 MPa
Split tensile strength of concrete + SF 1.0%	2.25 MPa
Split tensile strength of concrete + SF 1.5%	2.35 MPa

DISCUSSION

The concrete mix proportion used for preparing test specimens with a target compressive strength of 25 MPa [17] is presented in Table 4. The steel fiber content is expressed as a percentage of the sand weight.

Table 4. Concrete Mix Proportion

Cement	401.28 kg
Sand	651.38 kg
Gravel	1,147.44 kg
Water	181.40 kg
SF 0.5%	3.26 kg
SF 1.0%	6.51 kg
SF 1.5%	9.77 kg

Based on the experimental results, it was observed that the splitting tensile strength of concrete increased as the steel fiber content increased. This trend indicates that steel fibers contribute significantly to enhancing the tensile capacity of concrete. The mechanism behind this improvement is that steel fibers act as crack arrestors, bridging microcracks and delaying crack propagation. As a result, the material exhibits improved toughness, ductility, and resistance to tensile stresses.

However, in contrast to the positive impact on tensile strength, the compressive strength of concrete showed a decreasing trend with the increase in steel fiber content. This reduction can be attributed to several factors:

Excessive steel fibers can interfere with the compactness and homogeneity of the concrete mix. The fibers create microvoids and irregularities in the matrix, reducing the overall density and strength of the hardened concrete. As the fiber content increases, workability decreases, making it more difficult to achieve proper compaction. Poor workability can lead to fiber clumping, resulting in non-uniform distribution within the concrete, which negatively affects compressive strength. Steel fibers introduce additional interfaces within the concrete. Under compressive loading, stress concentrations may develop around these fibers, leading to localized failure and reducing the overall compressive strength of the material.

The relationship between steel fiber content and both splitting tensile strength and compressive strength is illustrated in the following graph:

CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results and analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The addition of steel fibers affects both the compressive and tensile strength of concrete, with differing trends for each mechanical property.

The optimal proportion of steel fiber in the concrete mix, considering mechanical performance, crack resistance, and sustainability, is found to be 0.5% of the sand weight. At this dosage, the tensile strength improvement is significant, while the reduction in compressive strength remains within an acceptable range.

The compressive strength of concrete decreases as the steel fiber content increases, likely due to disruptions in the concrete matrix and reduced compactness. In contrast, the tensile strength of concrete improves with higher steel fiber content, as the fibers help bridge cracks and enhance tensile resistance. This trade-off should be considered when designing fiber-reinforced concrete for structural applications, depending on whether tensile resistance, crack control, or compressive strength is the primary design concern..

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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